

Examining the Relationship Between Attitude Towards Artificial Intelligence, Readiness for Change and Intention to Leave¹

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between attitudes towards artificial intelligence, readiness for change, and intention to leave. In this study, the relational survey model, which is one of the quantitative research methods, was employed. The sample of the study consists of 159 employees working in the banking sector in Ankara. In the study, a four-part survey form was created using the demographic form developed by the researcher, "Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale", "Readiness for Change Scale", and "Intention to Leave Scale". The data analysis process was carried out using the SPSS 23 program. The Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale is quite reliable. According to the research findings, male participants have higher Positive Attitude and Artificial Intelligence Attitude scores compared to

female participants; they also stated that they are more open to change. The intention to leave the job of the 21-30 age group is higher than the 51-65 age group. As the income level increases and the level of AI usage increases, the readiness for change scores also increase. Paid users have the highest positive attitude and openness to change. While there is a positive relationship between AI Attitude and Readiness for Change, no significant relationship was found between the Intention to Leave and other variables

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Readiness for Change, Intention to Leave.

JEL Codes: M1

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1. Introduction

The rapid development of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies and their increasing integration into daily life make positive contributions to the quality of life of individuals and make human life easier in many areas. Artificial intelligence, which refers to the cognitive abilities exhibited by machines, is not only a technological revolution, but also a paradigm shift that reshapes the thinking, learning and decision-making processes of individuals (Wirth, 2018). AI research in computer science focuses on the development of systems that can mimic the biological intelligence and behavioural patterns of living things (Farrow, 2019). In this context, AI can be defined as the science and engineering of producing intelligent machines (McCarthy, 2007).

Artificial intelligence is generally considered as a technology that aims to enable machines to perform applications that are specific to human intelligence. When evaluated from a definitional perspective, AI can be expressed as the ability of a computer or robot to perform certain tasks like an intelligent living being. However, there are also approaches that go beyond this definition. According to Dereli (2020), AI is a system that not only accesses information but also learns by analyzing this information, adapts to its external environment and can perform the tasks assigned to it accordingly.

Jain (2018) defined artificial intelligence as “intelligence exhibited by machines, as opposed to human and animal intelligence” and stated that this technology has a structure that imitates the cognitive functions of the human mind, such as problem solving and learning. Looking from another perspective, Boden (2014) underlines that the main purpose of AI is to understand and illuminate mental processes rather than commercial gains.

The ultimate goal of AI studies is to develop systems that can perform human-like thinking, reasoning, learning and decision-making processes. In this context, Salvaris et al. (2018) define artificial intelligence as the effort to produce intelligent machines that have the capacity to simulate intelligence and imitate human behavior. Similarly, LExcellent (2019) considers this technology as the modeling of human intelligence by computer systems. Norvig (2012) defines AI as the most important general-purpose technology of our age, emphasizing that it has the ability to make the right choice in situations where humans cannot predict what to do. Brynjolfsson & McAfee (2017) state that the power of artificial intelligence comes from its ability to perform tasks with high performance without the need for human intervention and without the need to explain its operating logic in detail.

In this context, understanding individuals' attitudes towards artificial intelligence is very important in terms of analyzing the behavioral tendencies they develop towards the transformations brought about by the mentioned technology. Because individuals' attitudes towards AI are generally shaped by underlying beliefs, value judgments, and cognitive tendencies, and unless this structure changes, attitudes remain permanent (Çöllü & Öztürk, 2006). Especially in a period where radical technological changes such as artificial intelligence are on the agenda, one of the factors that determines the extent to which individuals are ready for this change is their attitudes towards AI (Çöllü & Öztürk, 2006; Çakan & Akın, 2024). Rafferty & Minbashian (2019) reveal that individuals' adaptation behaviors to technological innovations are affected by their perceptions and beliefs about these technologies. It can be said that individuals with positive attitudes approach change processes more openly and flexibly, whereas individuals with negative attitudes tend to resist these processes (Çakan & Akın, 2024).

It is thought that individuals' attitudes towards artificial intelligence are not only limited to their reactions to technological developments but may also be an indicator of the extent to which they are ready for change. The fact that transformative technologies such as artificial intelligence trigger change in many areas, from working styles to social relations, increases the importance of the attitudes and behaviors of individuals towards these transformation processes. Therefore, establishing a meaningful relationship between attitudes towards artificial intelligence and readiness for change plays a critical role in understanding both the individual adaptation process and corporate innovation management. Especially in today's world, where rapid technological transformations are taking place, determining the extent to which individuals are open to such innovations has become a fundamental requirement for the successful adoption of artificial intelligence-based systems.

Today, the dizzying pace of technological developments is transforming the habits of individuals and deeply affecting the operating dynamics of institutions. In particular, increasing investments in research and development activities, easier access to information, and the penetration of digitalization into every aspect of social life make change not only possible but also an inevitable reality. In this context, organizational change brings about radical transformations not only in processes but also in decision-making mechanisms, accountability, and redefinition of the institutional vision (Burke, 2017).

In this era where competition is intense and constant change has become the norm, the survival of organizations depends largely on their success in change

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management. However, it is a striking finding in the literature that most change processes do not achieve the desired level of success (Rafferty & Minbashian, 2019). The failure of organizational change efforts is often due to the lack of sufficient consideration of the human factor (Gürbüz & Bayık, 2019). This situation has led researchers to examine in depth the psychological, behavioral and attitudinal factors that affect the success of organizational change.

Especially today, artificial intelligence technologies, which are considered the driving force of change, play a central role in the transformation processes of organizations. In this new era where artificial intelligence-supported applications are radically transforming the way of doing business, the attitudes and psychological reactions of individuals in organizations towards this technology have a direct impact on the success of the change (Elias, 2009; Burke, 2017).

Factors such as employees' job satisfaction, stress level, and intention to leave are directly linked to perceptions and attitudes towards artificial intelligence. In this context, AI-based transformation processes should be evaluated not only with their technical and structural dimensions, but also with the psychological and emotional reactions of individuals (Elias, 2009).

In this context, it can be said that employees' attitudes towards artificial intelligence technologies may affect their level of adaptation to change and therefore, their tendency to leave their jobs. Individuals who view AI as a threat may begin to experience uncertainty about their professional future, which may increase their intention to leave their job. On the other hand, employees who perceive artificial intelligence as an opportunity and a supportive element are more open to change and maintain their level of organizational commitment. Therefore, individual attitudes become a determining factor not only in technological adaptation but also in employees' desire to remain in the organization (Rafferty & Minbashian, 2019).

From a business perspective, retaining qualified employees has become a strategic priority. The loss of talented, experienced employees who contribute to the organization at a high level can result in serious costs not only in terms of human resources but also in terms of knowledge, time and financial resources (Uyguç & Çımrın, 2004). For this reason, businesses should correctly analyze the reasons that trigger employees' tendency to leave their jobs, develop policies to minimize these risks, and carry out change processes with employee-centered approaches (Polat & Meydan, 2010).

In this context, the aim of the research is to examine the effects of individuals' attitudes towards ar-

tificial intelligence technologies on their readiness for change and intention to leave their job. The importance of the research lies in understanding the attitudes of individuals towards artificial intelligence and the dimensions of these attitudes related to openness to change and intention to leave the job in order to make organizational change sustainable in the process of rapid digitalization. It is thought that these findings will contribute to the shaping of human resources policies and the development of change management strategies in a human-oriented manner in both public and private sector organizations.

The hypotheses of this research are as follows:

- H1: The attitudes of banking sector employees towards artificial intelligence differ according to demographic factors (gender, age, education level, household income status, length of service in the sector, use of paid artificial intelligence products).
- H2: The readiness of banking sector employees for change varies according to demographic factors (gender, age, education level, household income level, length of service in the sector, use of paid artificial intelligence products).
- H3: The intentions of banking sector employees to leave their jobs vary according to demographic factors (gender, age, education level, household income level, length of service in the sector, use of paid artificial intelligence products).
- H4: There is a statistically significant relationship between the attitudes of banking sector employees towards artificial intelligence and their readiness for change.
- H5: There is a statistically significant relationship between the attitudes of banking sector employees towards artificial intelligence and their intention to leave their job.
- H6: There is a statistically significant relationship between the readiness for change of banking sector employees and their intention to leave their jobs.

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

In this study, the relational screening model, which is within the scope of quantitative research methods, was used. The model in question is defined as a screening design that allows the determination and interpretation of relationships between multiple variables (Şimşek, 2012). The model of the research is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Model

2.2. Universe and Sample

The population of the study consists of employees working in the banking sector in Ankara. The main reason for conducting the research in the banking sector is that it has a structure in which intense work tempo, high stress level and customer relations are at the forefront. The sample of the study consists of 159 employees working in the banking sector in Ankara. The sample size was determined based on a 95% confidence level. Simple random sampling method was preferred in selecting the sample.

2.3. Data Collection Tools

In the study, a survey form consisting of four sections was created using the demographic form developed by the researcher, the "Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale", the "Readiness for Change Scale" and the "Intention to Leave Scale". These scales are as follows;

Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale: The "Computer Attitude Scale", which was developed by Nickell & Pinto (1986) and aimed to measure individuals' attitudes and beliefs towards computers, was updated and re-adapted by Durndell & Haag (2002) in the following years as the "Internet Attitude Scale". This adaptation aimed to expand the scope of the scale in parallel with technological developments and to evaluate attitudes towards internet use. This scale was translated into Turkish as "Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale" by Çakan & Akın (2024) in line with technological developments. The scale consists of two sub-dimensions that aim to measure positive and negative attitudes towards artificial intelligence and contains a total of 12 items. A 5-point Likert-type measurement system is used for participants to rate their opinions.

Readiness for Change Scale: The "Readiness for Change" scale developed by Rafferty & Minbashian (2019) was designed to assess individuals' readiness levels for organizational change. This scale was adapted into Turkish and made available by Çakan & Akın (2024). The single-dimensional scale contains

a total of 5 items and a 7-point Likert-type rating system is used to measure the attitudes of the participants.

Intention to Leave Scale: The scale developed by Reychav & Weisberg (2009) was created to measure individuals' attitudes and tendencies towards a specific issue. The scale in question was adapted to Turkish by Büyükbeşe (2012) and made suitable for use in the local context. The single-dimensional scale contains a total of 8 items, and a 5-point Likert-type scaling method is used to rate participants' opinions.

2.4. Analysis of Data

The data analysis process was carried out using the SPSS 23 program. Firstly, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was calculated to evaluate the reliability of the scales used. The conformity of the data to normal distribution was tested before moving on to difference analyses; parametric test methods were preferred in the analyses in line with the findings obtained. In order to determine significant differences between scale scores according to demographic variables, t-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) for independent samples were used. Correlation analysis was applied to reveal the level and direction of the relationships between the scales.

2.5. Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is one of the basic reliability indicators used to evaluate the internal consistency of a scale and takes values between 0 and 1. In the interpretation of this coefficient, the following ranges are generally taken into account: 0.00–0.40 indicates low reliability, 0.40–0.60 indicates limited reliability, 0.60–0.80 indicates a highly reliable structure, and 0.80–1.00 indicates a high level of reliability (Tavşancıl, 2005). In this context, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is considered an important criterion in determining the consistency and reliability of the scale on the structure it measures.

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Table 1 . Reliability Analysis

	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Negative Attitude	7	0.937
Positive Attitude	5	0.936
Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	12	0.778
Readiness for Change Scale	5	0.974
Intention to Leave Scale	8	0.919

The table presents the Cronbach Alpha coefficients obtained within the scope of reliability analyses of the scales used and their sub-dimensions. According to the values obtained; Positive Attitude and Nega-

tive Attitude sub-dimensions, Readiness for Change Scale and Intention to Leave Scale were found to be highly reliable. Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale has a generally very high level of reliability.

Table 2. Personal Information

		n	%
Gender	Female	88	55.3
	Male	71	44.7
Age	21-30	14	8.8
	31-40	26	16.4
	41-50	62	39.0
	51-65	57	35.8
Education Status	High School	6	3.8
	Associate Degree	11	6.9
	Bachelor's Degree	83	52.2
	Postgraduate	59	37.1
Household Income Status	Less than 30.000 TL	6	3.8
	Between 30.001-40.000 TL	9	5.7
	Between 40.001-50.000 TL	22	13.8
	Over 50.000 TL	122	76.7
Duration of Employment in the Sector	1 year or less	16	10.1
	2-5 years	8	5.0
	6-10 years	12	7.5
	11-15 years	18	11.3
	16 years and over	105	66.0
Use of Paid Artificial Intelligence Products	None	75	47.2
	I use the free versions	64	40.3
	I have a paid membership	20	12.6

Table 2 shows the distribution of participants' personal characteristics. 55.3% of the participants are female and 44.7% are male. The most densely populated age group is the 41-50 age group with 39.0%, followed by the 51-65 age group with 35.8%. 52.2% of the participants have a bachelor's degree, 37.1% have a postgraduate degree, 6.9% have an associate's degree, and 3.8% have a high school degree. When looking at household income, it is seen that the vast majority (76.7%) have an income of over

50.000 TL. When the distribution of participants in terms of their working years in the sector is examined, it is striking that 66.0% have 16 years or more of experience. This group is followed by 11.3% with 11-15 years and 10.1% with 1 year or less of experience. When looking at the status of using paid artificial intelligence products, 47.2% of the participants stated that they do not use any artificial intelligence products, 40.3% use only free versions, and 12.6% have paid memberships.

3. Findings

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics

	avg.	sd.	min.	max.	skewness	kurtosis
Negative Attitude	21,45	7,55	7	35	0,004	-0,724
Positive Attitude	16,55	5,77	5	25	-0,454	-0,648
Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	38,00	8,27	19	60	0,557	0,467
Readiness for Change Scale	20,62	8,52	5	35	-0,087	-1,081
Intention to Leave Scale	19,03	7,94	8	40	0,67	-0,068

Skewness and kurtosis values were calculated to determine the conformity of the data related to the scales and their sub-dimensions to normal distribution. According to the widely accepted approach in the literature, when these values are between -2 and +2, it is interpreted that the data are normally distributed (Hopkins & Weeks, 1990; De Carlo, 1997). As a result of the analysis, the relevant values of all scales and their sub-dimensions are within this range and it is accepted that the data are normally distributed. In this direction, parametric test methods were used in statistical analyses.

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Table 4. Comparison of Scale and Sub-Dimension Scores in Terms of Participants' Gender

	Female		Male		t	p
	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.		
Negative Attitude	20,94	7,53	22,08	7,57	-0,948	0,345
Positive Attitude	15,67	5,93	17,63	5,42	-2,156	0,033*
Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	36,61	7,28	39,72	9,11	-2,333	0,021*
Readiness for Change Scale	19,30	8,45	22,25	8,38	-2,203	0,029*
Intention to Leave Scale	19,14	7,68	18,89	8,30	0,196	0,845

Table 4 shows the independent sample t-test results for comparing the Positive/Negative Attitude sub-dimension scores, Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale, Readiness for Change Scale and Intention to Leave Scale scores according to the gender of the participants. In terms of Positive Attitude, male participants had significantly higher scores than female participants. Male participants also had significantly higher scores than female participants in the total

score of the Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale. A significant difference was also found in the scores of the Readiness for Change Scale according to gender. Male participants had higher scores indicating that they were more open and ready for change. No significant difference was found in the Negative Attitude sub-dimension and Intention to Leave scales according to gender.

Table 5. Comparison of Scale and Sub-Dimension Scores in Terms of Participants' Ages

	21-30		31-40		41-50		51-65		F	p
	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.		
Negative Attitude	22,43	8,98	22,23	6,39	20,74	7,84	21,63	7,46	0,360	0,782
Positive Attitude	15,71	7,10	18,04	5,06	17,19	5,25	15,37	6,15	1,717	0,177
Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	38,14	9,81	40,27	8,94	37,94	8,53	37,00	7,21	0,933	0,426
Readiness for Change Scale	21,93	8,40	23,04	7,77	20,50	8,70	19,32	8,62	1,264	0,289
Intention to Leave Scale	24,07	7,39	20,27	5,74	18,40	8,47	17,89	7,97	2,695	0,048*

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Table 5 shows the ANOVA test results for comparing the Positive/Negative Attitude sub-dimension scores, Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale, Readiness for Change Scale and Intention to Leave Scale scores of the participants according to their age groups. In line with the findings, a statistically significant difference was found only in the Intention to Leave Scale scores according to the age variable.

Participants in the 21-30 age group had significantly higher scores on the Intention to Leave Scale com-

pared to those in the 51-65 age group.

When the Negative Attitude and Positive Attitude sub-dimensions and the Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and Readiness for Change Scale scores were examined, it was seen that there was no statistically significant difference between age groups. This finding reveals that individuals, regardless of their age, show similar tendencies in their attitudes towards artificial intelligence and their levels of openness to change.

Table 6. Comparison of Scale and Sub-Dimension Scores in Terms of Participants' Educational Status

	High School		Associate Degree		Bachelor's Degree		Postgraduate		F	p
	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.		
Negative Attitude	23,67	10,42	22,18	4,94	21,64	7,15	20,83	8,25	0,275	0,842
Positive Attitude	14,67	7,28	13,91	5,96	16,10	5,53	17,86	5,75	2,220	0,088
Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	38,33	10,73	36,09	4,46	37,73	7,90	38,69	9,12	0,362	0,781
Readiness for Change Scale	12,33	10,05	18,45	7,87	21,28	7,78	20,93	9,17	2,381	0,072
Intention to Leave Scale	13,50	6,95	21,09	6,89	19,04	7,88	19,19	8,21	1,231	0,300

Table 6 shows the ANOVA test results for comparing the Positive/Negative Attitude sub-dimension scores, Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale, Readiness for Change Scale and Intention to Leave Scale scores

according to the participants' educational status. As a result of the analysis, no statistically significant difference was found in terms of all variables according to the level of education ($p>0.05$).

Table 7. Comparison of Scale and Sub-Dimension Scores in Terms of Household Income Status of Participants

	Less than 30.000 TL		Between 30.001-40.000 TL		Between 40.001-50.000 TL		Over 50.000 TL		F	p
	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.		
Negative Attitude	19,33	9,85	25,11	7,96	19,73	8,18	21,60	7,26	1,268	0,287
Positive Attitude	17,00	7,13	14,44	6,00	15,64	5,83	16,84	5,71	0,696	0,556
Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	36,33	9,67	39,56	9,74	35,36	6,68	38,44	8,34	1,051	0,372
Readiness for Change Scale	15,00	10,58	19,00	8,94	16,64	8,82	21,73	8,09	3,422	0,019*
Intention to Leave Scale	21,17	10,74	22,33	7,04	22,00	9,03	18,14	7,53	2,255	0,084

Table 7 shows the ANOVA test results for comparing the Negative Attitude sub-dimension, Positive Attitude sub-dimension, Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale, Readiness for Change Scale and Intention to Leave Scale scores according to the household income status of the participants.

According to the findings, a statistically significant difference was found in the Readiness for Change Scale scores ($p=0.019$). In terms of the Readiness for Change Scale, a significant difference was found between individuals in the 40.001–50.000 TL income group and individuals with an income of 50.000 TL

and above.

When the Negative Attitude and Positive Attitude sub-dimensions and the Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and the Intention to Leave Scale scores were examined, it was determined that there was no

statistically significant difference depending on the income level ($p > 0.05$). This situation reveals that the participants did not show a significant difference in their attitudes and tendencies towards the variables in question according to their income levels.

Table 8. Comparison of Scale and Sub-Dimension Scores in Terms of Participants' Working Time in the Sector

	1 year or less		2-5 years		6-10 years		11-15 years		16 years and over		F	p
	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.		
Negative Attitude	21,50	8,41	24,88	6,10	23,17	7,47	21,83	6,09	20,92	7,76	0,701	0,592
Positive Attitude	15,19	6,87	19,13	5,94	16,92	5,70	16,06	5,27	16,60	5,71	0,662	0,619
Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	36,69	9,91	44,00	7,43	40,08	9,35	37,89	8,91	37,52	7,74	1,450	0,220
Readiness for Change Scale	20,31	9,60	24,25	6,09	19,42	9,09	24,22	7,96	19,90	8,45	1,433	0,226
Intention to Leave Scale	24,56	7,72	21,50	7,05	17,92	5,50	19,22	7,74	18,09	8,04	2,679	0,034*

Table 8 shows the ANOVA test results comparing the Positive/Negative Attitude sub-dimension scores, Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale, Readiness for Change Scale and Intention to Leave Scale scores of the participants according to their length of service in the sector. According to the analysis findings, a

significant difference was found only in the Intention to Leave Scale scores. Intention to Leave Scale scores were significantly higher in participants who had been working in the sector for 1 year or less than in participants with 16 years or more experience.

Table 9. Comparison of Scale and Sub-Dimension Scores in Terms of Participants' Use of Paid Artificial Intelligence Products

	None		I use the free versions		I have a paid membership		F	p
	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.	avg.	sd.		
Negative Attitude	20,01	7,28	21,73	7,86	25,95	5,70	5,227	0,006*
Positive Attitude	15,28	5,19	17,33	5,63	18,80	7,32	4,066	0,019*
Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	35,29	6,96	39,06	7,73	44,75	10,04	10,137	0,000*
Readiness for Change Scale	16,33	7,34	23,56	7,14	27,25	8,75	25,334	0,000*
Intention to Leave Scale	18,16	8,02	20,75	7,90	16,75	6,91	2,843	0,061

Table 9 shows the ANOVA test results for comparing the Negative Attitude sub-dimension, Positive Attitude sub-dimension, Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale, Readiness for Change Scale and Intention to Leave Scale scores according to the participants' use of paid artificial intelligence products. Accordingly, significant differences were found in the Negative Attitude sub-dimension, Positive Attitude sub-dimension, Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and Readiness for Change Scale ($p < 0.05$).

A significant difference was observed in Negative Attitude scores. The negative attitude scores of paid AI users are significantly higher than those who do not use AI. The difference is also significant in terms of Positive Attitude. Paid users have higher positive attitude scores than non-users. Significant differences were found between all groups in the total score of the AI Attitude Scale. It is observed that as the level of AI use increases, attitude scores also increase. The highest average is in the group with

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paid membership. The Readiness for Change Scale scores differ significantly between the groups. Paid users exhibit a profile that is more open to change compared to both free users and non-users. In terms of the Intention to Leave Scale, the difference

is quite close to the significance level, but it is not statistically significant. However, the striking point is that this scale score is seen as the highest in the free user group and the lowest in the paid user group.

Table 10. Correlation Analysis of Scale and Sub-Dimension Scores

		Negative Attitude	Positive Attitude	Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	Readiness for Change Scale	Intention to Leave Scale
Negative Attitude	r	-				
	p					
Positive Attitude	r	-,252**				
	p	0,001				
Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale	r	,737**	,469**			
	p	0,000	0,000			
Readiness for Change Scale	r	,301**	,392**	,549**		
	p	0,000	0,000	0,000		
Intention to Leave Scale	r	0,028	0,077	0,080	0,091	-
	p	0,722	0,332	0,316	0,253	

**.: $p < 0,01$

Table 10 shows the results of the Pearson correlation analysis conducted to determine the relationships between the scales and their sub-dimensions. The correlation coefficients obtained reveal the direction and strength of the relationship between the variables. According to Yazicioğlu & Erdoğan (2014), the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient is an important criterion in interpreting the level of relationship. Accordingly, if the correlation coefficient is in the range of 0.00–0.25, the relationship is considered very weak, in the range of 0.26–0.49, it is considered weak, in the range of 0.50–0.69, it is considered moderate, in the range of 0.70–0.89, it is considered high, and in the range of 0.90–1.00, it is considered very high. This classification provides a basic reference for understanding the strength of the relationship between variables. Accordingly;

It was determined that there was a weak, positive and statistically significant relationship between the Negative Attitude and the Readiness for Change Scale ($r = 0.301$; $p < 0.001$). This finding shows that individuals with negative attitudes can still be open to change to a certain extent. Similarly, a weak, positive and significant relationship was found between the Positive Attitude and the Readiness for Change Scale ($r = 0.392$; $p < 0.001$). This result indicates that individuals who develop a positive attitude towards artificial intelligence are more ready for change processes. The relationship between the Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and the Readiness for Change Scale was found to be moderate, positive and statistically significant ($r = 0.549$; $p < 0.001$). This shows that positive attitudes towards artificial intelligence

in general increase the level of individuals' adoption of change. On the other hand, no statistically significant relationship was found between the Intention to Leave Scale and the Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and its sub-dimensions ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, no statistically significant relationship was found between the Intention to Leave Scale and the Readiness for Change Scale ($p > 0.05$). These results reveal that the intention to leave does not show a direct relationship with the other variables examined.

4. Conclusion and Discussion

In this section, statistical analyses regarding the findings obtained within the scope of the research are presented and the relationships between the variables are evaluated in detail.

In terms of Positive Attitude, male participants scored significantly higher than female participants. This shows that male participants have a more positive attitude towards AI. Male participants also scored significantly higher than female participants in the total score of the AI Attitude Scale. This finding shows that male participants generally have a more positive and accepting perspective towards AI.

This result is consistent with similar studies in the literature. For example, Çankaya (2024) and Kandemir & Azizoğlu (2024) stated that male individuals have a more positive attitude towards artificial intelligence compared to females. Similarly, Figueiredo (2019), Zhang & Dafoe (2019), Sindermann et al. (2022), and Fietta et al. (2021) also found that men have a more accepting and positive perspective towards tech-

nological innovations. These findings suggest that gender is an effective variable in shaping attitudes towards technology.

On the other hand, it was found that male participants received significantly higher scores than female participants in terms of the Readiness for Change Scale. This shows that male individuals are more open and prepared for innovations and technological transformations. However, this finding contradicts some studies. For example, Helvacı & Kıcıroğlu (2010) and Levent (2016) stated that gender does not have a significant effect on readiness for change. This difference may be due to the professional, cultural or demographic characteristics of the study groups, or it may be related to the transformation of technological awareness and social roles over time.

Participants in the 21-30 age group have significantly higher scores on the Intention to Leave Scale than those in the 51-65 age group. This finding shows that individuals in the younger age group have a stronger intention to leave their jobs. It is thought that individuals, especially those in their early career period, may be more likely to be open to alternative job opportunities, re-evaluate career development, or leave their current jobs due to fluctuations in job satisfaction. This finding is consistent with the existing literature. Lewis (1991) and Khanin (2013) stated that older employees are less likely to leave their jobs than their younger counterparts. Similarly, Cho & Song (2017) emphasized that individuals' intention to leave decreases as the time they spend in their organization increases, meaning that tenure has a negative effect on intention to leave. In this respect, it can be said that variables such as age and seniority play an important role in determining the tendency to leave the job.

According to the research findings, no statistically significant difference was found between age groups in terms of Negative Attitude, Positive Attitude, Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and Readiness for Change Scale scores. This result conveys that the attitudes of individuals in different age groups towards artificial intelligence and their levels of readiness for change are largely similar. This result is similar to some studies. For example, Çankaya (2024) did not find any significant difference depending on the age variable in terms of the Positive and Negative Attitude sub-dimensions and the total score of the Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale. Similarly, Yakut (2024) and Elsayed & Sleem (2021) did not find statistically significant differences in attitudes towards artificial intelligence between age groups. Şentürk & Köklü (2013) also stated that age is not a determining variable in terms of readiness for change. On the other hand, the literature on this subject is not homogeneous. In particular, some studies show that younger individuals have a more positive attitude towards artificial intelligence. A study con-

ducted by YouGov (2023) in the USA determined that the group that uses artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT most intensively is between the ages of 18-29. Similarly, Swed et al. (2022) found that the majority of individuals aged 21-30 had a positive approach towards AI. Kandemir & Azizoğlu (2024) emphasized that the positive attitude scores of individuals aged 45 and over were significantly lower compared to younger age groups. In addition, Sabra et al. (2023) found that nurses aged 25-35 had more positive attitudes, while those aged 35 and over had more negative attitudes. When looking at the relationship between the age variable and readiness for change, Er (2013) and Levent (2016) stated that young individuals are more open to change and that this situation is inversely proportional to age. Such results suggest that factors such as digital literacy, adaptability and openness to innovation, which are inherent in technological transformations, work in favor of young individuals. In conclusion, although no significant age-related difference was observed in this study, the findings in the literature provide various evidence suggesting that especially young individuals develop more positive attitudes towards artificial intelligence technologies and change.

As a result of the analyses performed, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference according to the level of education in terms of all variables examined. It can be said that this result reveals that individuals' attitudes towards artificial intelligence and their levels of openness to change are similar regardless of their academic qualifications. This result is consistent with some national and international studies. For example, Kandemir & Azizoğlu (2024) and Çankaya (2024) did not find a significant relationship between attitude scales towards artificial intelligence and education level. Similarly, in a study conducted in Lebanon, Doumat et al. (2022) stated that there was no significant difference between individuals' academic levels and their attitude scores towards artificial intelligence. In terms of readiness for change, Levent (2016) revealed that the level of education was not a determining factor. On the other hand, some studies present results that partially contradict these findings. For example, in the study conducted by Akyazı (2023) with white-collar workers in Aksaray, while no significant difference was found in terms of education level in the Negative Attitude sub-dimension, it was found that the positive attitude scores of undergraduate graduates were higher than those of primary and secondary school graduates. Similarly, in the study conducted by Yakut (2024) in Ankara, it was determined that individuals with postgraduate education had higher positive attitudes towards artificial intelligence compared to primary school graduates.

According to the research results, a significant difference was found in terms of the Readiness for

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Change Scale scores according to the income levels of the participants. In particular, it was determined that individuals in the income group of 50.000 TL and above were more ready for change compared to individuals with incomes in the range of 40.001–50.000 TL. This situation shows that income level can have an impact on the openness of individuals to innovations and transformations. The fact that individuals embrace change more easily as income level increases can be explained by the fact that they have structural advantages such as financial security, education and access to technology. Individuals in higher income groups are likely to be more flexible and motivated to follow and adapt to technological developments, resulting in a higher level of readiness for change.

No significant difference was found in the Negative Attitude sub-dimension, Positive Attitude sub-dimension, Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and Intention to Leave Scale variables according to income level. This result reveals that individuals' attitudes towards artificial intelligence and their intention to leave their jobs are similar regardless of their income level. This finding is consistent with some studies in the literature. In fact, in the research conducted by Yakut (2024), no significant difference was found between the Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and its sub-dimensions and the income levels of individuals. This indicates that the level of economic well-being may not be a determining factor on the perception and attitudes of individuals towards technology.

The Intention to Leave Scale scores are significantly higher among participants who have been working in the sector for 1 year or less than those with 16 years or more experience. This finding shows that those who are new to the sector have a higher intention to leave, and this intention decreases as they gain experience. It can be thought that individuals, especially those at the beginning of their professional lives, are more likely to leave their jobs due to reasons such as not yet having fully formed institutional ties, low job satisfaction, or reshaping their career expectations. This finding is also consistent with the existing literature. In fact, studies conducted by Selçuk & Seren (2024) and Boz (2024) have revealed that individuals who are new to the sector have a higher intention to leave their jobs. This situation shows that factors such as uncertainty, difficulty in adaptation and unfulfilled expectations experienced in the early stages of business life can make individuals more prone to question their current jobs.

In the studies conducted by Selamat et al. (2021), Swed et al. (2022), Kandemir & Azizoğlu (2024) and Çankaya (2024), no statistically significant relationship was found between attitudes towards artificial intelligence and length of service in the sector. These findings show that individuals' attitudes toward

artificial intelligence are shaped independently of professional seniority. Similarly, in the research conducted by Levent (2016), it was stated that there was no significant difference between readiness for change and sectoral experience. In this respect, it can be said that individual responses to technological developments and institutional changes are determined not only by professional experience but also by factors such as personal characteristics, education, level of exposure to technology and individual attitudes.

A significant difference was observed in Negative Attitude scores. Paid AI users had significantly higher negative attitude scores than non-AI users. This finding suggests that active users may also carry critical or cautious views towards technology. The difference is also significant in terms of Positive Attitude. Paid users have higher positive attitude scores compared to non-users. This shows that individuals who interact with AI more evaluate the technology more positively. Significant differences were found among all groups in the total score of the Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale. It is observed that as the level of artificial intelligence use increases, attitude scores also increase. The highest average is in the group with paid membership. The findings are consistent with the studies in the literature. For example, Çankaya (2024) stated that individuals who have knowledge about artificial intelligence have higher positive attitudes, but there is no significant difference in terms of negative attitudes. Similarly, Karacan Doğan et al. (2023) also revealed that participants with higher general knowledge levels develop more positive attitudes towards artificial intelligence. These results show that the level of interaction and knowledge with artificial intelligence technologies is an important determinant of individual attitudes.

The scores on the Readiness for Change Scale differ significantly between the groups. Paid users exhibit a profile that is more open to change compared to both free users and non-users. This finding shows that individuals with access to digital technologies are generally more open to innovation. In terms of the Intention to Leave Scale, the difference is very close to the significance level, but it is not statistically significant. However, it is noteworthy that this scale score is highest in the free user group and lowest in the paid user group. This can be interpreted as individuals who work more integrated with technology may be more committed to their jobs.

A weak positive and significant relationship was found between Negative Attitude and Readiness for Change Scale ($r = 0.301$; $p < 0.001$). A weak positive and significant relationship was found between Positive Attitude and Readiness for Change Scale ($r = 0.392$; $p < 0.001$). A moderately positive and significant relationship was found between Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and Readiness for Change

Scale ($r = 0.549$; $p < 0.001$). This finding shows that general attitudes towards artificial intelligence are a stronger determinant of openness to change. A positive general perspective towards artificial intelligence technologies enables individuals to adopt innovations more easily and be more willing to adapt. The findings are consistent with some studies in the literature. Çakan & Akın (2024) revealed in their study that there is a positive and significant relationship between attitudes towards artificial intelligence and individuals' readiness for change. This finding shows that individuals who develop a positive attitude towards technological developments also exhibit a profile that is more open to change. Similarly, Rafferty & Minbashian (2019) stated that individuals' beliefs about change are one of the basic antecedents of readiness for change and emphasized that these beliefs are directly related to the technological adaptation process. In addition, in the research conducted by Irimia-Diéguez et al. (2023), it was stated that the positive attitudes of employees towards innovative technologies significantly increase the intention to adopt and use these technologies. These findings show that attitudes have an impact not only on perceptual levels but also on behavioral tendencies.

There was no statistically significant relationship between the Intention to Leave Scale and the Artificial Intelligence Attitude Scale and its sub-dimensions ($p > 0.05$). Accordingly, it is thought that individuals' attitudes towards artificial intelligence do not have a direct determining effect on their intention to leave their jobs. However, this result differs from some studies in the literature. In fact, in the study conducted by Kılıç (2023), it was revealed that there was a low-level but positive and statistically significant relationship between employees' awareness of artificial intelligence and their intention to leave their jobs. This finding suggests that the integration of AI technologies into business processes may be associated with factors such as uncertainty, job loss anxiety, or task changes for some employees. Similarly, Li et al. (2019) found a significant relationship between employees' AI awareness and their intention to leave their jobs.

No statistically significant relationship was found between the Intention to Leave Scale and the Readiness for Change Scale ($p > 0.05$). Although readiness for change is a feature that facilitates adaptation to organizational innovation processes, it may not be a determining factor in individuals' decisions to leave their current jobs. This finding is consistent with some studies in the literature. For example, Neves (2009) stated that employees' readiness for change is not directly related to their intention to leave their job, but rather has an indirect effect through emotional commitment to change. Similarly, Cunningham (2006) reported that there was no statistically significant relationship between individuals' commitment

to change and their intention to leave their jobs. This result shows that commitment to change does not affect employees' intention to leave their jobs in all cases.

In line with the research findings, it is recommended that institutions organize awareness and training programs for employees in order to improve attitudes towards artificial intelligence. In particular, inclusive approaches should be adopted to support female employees in developing positive attitudes towards technology. The fact that young employees have higher intentions to leave their jobs reveals the importance of career planning, supportive leadership and commitment-enhancing practices specific to this group. In addition, the fact that individuals who interact more with artificial intelligence technologies have higher levels of positive attitudes and openness to change indicates that employees should be actively introduced to these technologies. Finally, considering the difference between income level and readiness for change, supportive programs should be developed to facilitate the adaptation of employees in the low-income group to change processes.

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